

Physicochemical Study of Some Transition Metal Complexes of Vanillin-sulphanilate

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Transition metal complexes of a Schiff base, derived from vanillin and sulphanic acid (Van-Sul), have been prepared and characterised on the basis of element analysis, infrared and electronic spectra and magnetic susceptibility measurements. The magnetic and spectral data indicate them to be low spin octahedral complexes. Van-Sul molecules apparently act as the bidentate O-O donor.

SCHIFF bases containing two or more chromophoric groups separated by only one single bond (i.e. forming a conjugated system) are important not only for their analytical and physiological uses, but also for their interesting spectral and unusual magnetic and structural properties. In continuation of our studies¹⁻³ on transition metal complexes of Schiff bases derived from vanillin, we report here the results of our studies on the synthesis and characterisation of Fe(II), Co(II), Ni(II), Cu(II), Mn(II) and Fe(III) complexes of Van-Sul.

Experimental

All the chemical used were AR or SM reagents.

Preparation of Van-Sul: On refluxing aqueous solutions of sulphanilic acid and vanillin (hot water) in equimolar ratio, yellow coloured Schiff base, $C_8H_8(OH)(OCH_3)CH=NC_6H_4SO_3H$, separated out, m.p. 272° with decomposition, soluble in alkali, alcohol and dioxan.

Preparation of the metal complexes: Metal complexes of the Schiff base were prepared by refluxing aqueous solutions of the metal salt and sodium salt of the Schiff base in 1 : 2 molar ratio for 2 to 3 hr. The metal salts used were $CuSO_4 \cdot 5H_2O$, $NiSO_4 \cdot 7H_2O$, $MnSO_4 \cdot 7H_2O$, $Fe(NH_4)_2(SO_4)_2 \cdot 6H_2O$, $Fe(NO_3)_3 \cdot 9H_2O$ and $CoSO_4 \cdot 7H_2O$. Sodium salt of the Schiff base used was prepared by dissolving the Schiff base in the least quantity of a dilute solution of NaOH. The insoluble complexes that separated out on cooling, were filtered, washed, dried in vacuum and analysed for percentage of the metal, C, H, N and S microanalytically.

Results and Discussion

The analytical data and conductometric study indicate 1 : 2 metal : ligand stoichiometry, with the molecular formula $ML_2 \cdot 2H_2O$, for all the complexes except the iron complex which was shown to have $ML_2(OH) \cdot H_2O$ formula. The isolated complexes

were insoluble in common organic solvents and water and were infusible below 300°. The magnetic and spectral data indicate these complexes to be low spin ones in which Van-Sul molecules are attached with the metal ion through the phenolic and methoxy oxygen of the vanillin residue and imparting octahedral geometry to the complexes.

Magnetic moments and electronic spectra :

Mn(II)-Van-Sul: The μ_{eff} value (1.7 B.M.) obtained for the complex at room temperature (24°), is well within the range of low-spin octahedral stereochemistry. The electronic spectra of the complex exhibit only two bands at 18.5 kK and 23.2 kK. These low energy bands arising from the ground state ${}^6A_{1g}(I)$ may be assigned to ${}^6A_{1g}(I) \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}(I)$ and ${}^6A_{1g}(I) \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(I)$ transitions respectively, characteristic of octahedral geometry of Mn(II) complexes⁴.

Iron complexes: The magnetic moment value obtained for the Van-Sul complex isolated with the Fe(II) salt, is quite abnormal (2.0 B.M.) and is the same as obtained for Fe(III)-Van-Sul (1.97 B.M.). This indicates oxidation of Fe(II) into Fe(III) during isolation, as is also observed in the cases of Van-Hy⁵ and Van-An³ complexes of the salt. The μ_{eff} value of 2.0 B.M. is well within the range reported for spin-paired octahedral complexes of Fe(III)^{5,6}. Conclusion that Fe(II) is oxidised to Fe(III) is supported by the electronic and infrared spectra (discussed below) of the complex. The electronic spectra of the complex obtained with the Fe(II) salt show two bands at 17.2 and 20.0 kK which are quite analogous to the band obtained in case of Fe(III) complexes with octahedral stereochemistry⁷. These bands can be assigned to ${}^2T_{2g} \rightarrow {}^6A_{1g}$ transitions of Fe(III) complexes in octahedral environment. This band in Fe(III) Van-Sul appears at 17.2 kK, in addition to a band at 13.7 kK for the ${}^2T_{2g} \rightarrow {}^6A_{1g}$ transition. Since the complex isolated with the Fe(II) salt

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did not show any band in the regions 10.5 and 8.0 kK [characteristic of Fe(II) complexes in octahedral stereochemistry], it is clear in the light of the magnetic and spectral studies, that the two complexes of iron isolated in this study have Fe(III) in octahedral stereochemistry.

Co(II)-Van-Sul : The μ_{eff} value (1.78 B.M.) of Co(II)-Van-Sul is characteristic of low-spin octahedral complexes of Co(II). The electronic spectra of the complex indicate two bands, one at 18.9 kK and the other at 20.48 kK and may be assigned to ${}^2E_g(G) \rightarrow {}^2T_{1g}(G)$ and ${}^2E_g(G) \rightarrow {}^2T_{1g}$ transitions respectively in octahedral field⁸.

Ni(II)-Van-Sul : The magnetic moment of the complex (3.2 B.M.) indicates it to be an octahedral complex⁹. However, the value is higher than that of a typical paramagnetic octahedral Ni(II) complex⁹ and indicates large orbital contribution. The octahedral stereochemistry of the complex is also indicated by the two absorption bands seen in its electronic spectra for the transition ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(F)$ (16.1 kK) and ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(P)$ (28.5 kK).

Cu(II)-Van-Sul : The μ_{eff} value obtained for the complex (1.85 B.M.) is greater than the spin only value (1.7 B.M.) and indicates orbital contribution and distortion of octahedral structure. This complex did not give any band in visible region as d-d transitions are obscured by the intense C.T. bands.

IR spectra : Infrared spectra of the complexes show that the bands due to $\nu(OH)$, appearing at 3440, 3180 and 2840 cm^{-1} in the free ligand, fuse and become broad in the region 3600-2800 cm^{-1} . The $\nu(C-O)$ due to methoxy group, appearing in the region 1240-1290 cm^{-1} in the free ligand, is lowered by 15-30 cm^{-1} in the complexes while $\nu(C-O)$ due to phenolic OH group is shifted to higher frequency by 10-20 cm^{-1} in the complexes than in the free ligand. This shows that complexation take place through phenolic OH group with deprotonation¹⁰ and oxygen of the methoxy group. The $\nu(S-O)$, and

symmetric and asymmetric $\nu(SO_2)$ remain unchanged in the regions 1180, 980 and 1040 cm^{-1} , respectively¹¹. The coordinated water in the complexes is indicated by the presence of bands at ~ 3200 , 1600 and 840 cm^{-1} ^{12,13} while the M-O band appears at ~ 455 cm^{-1} in the complexes¹⁴.

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